

INFLAMMATORY AND ANGIOGENIC ACTIVATION IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF COMPLICATED ADHESIVE INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Systemic inflammation and vascular remodeling are key elements in the development of complications in AIO. Biomarkers of angiogenesis and cytokine activation reflect the severity of tissue damage and ischemia. Studying their dynamics helps to predict clinical outcomes and tailor therapy.

Relevance: Systemic inflammation and vascular remodeling are key elements in the development of complications in AIO. Biomarkers of angiogenesis and cytokine activation reflect the severity of tissue damage and ischemia. Studying their dynamics helps to predict clinical outcomes and tailor therapy.

Objective: To investigate the inflammatory and angiogenic profiles in patients with complicated AIO.

Materials and Methods: A total of 53 patients with complicated AIO and 30 healthy controls were studied. Serum levels of IL-6, IL-18, TNF- α , VEGF-A, and TGF- β were measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Statistical comparisons were performed with significance set at $p < 0.01$.

Results: IL-18 levels increased 3.6 times, IL-6 doubled, and TNF- α rose by 1.8 times in patients compared to controls. VEGF-A and TGF- β were also significantly elevated by 1.8 and 2.6 times, respectively. Correlation analysis showed strong positive links between VEGF-A and IL-18 ($r = 0.80$), and between TGF- β and TNF- α ($r = 0.81$). These markers reflect a simultaneous activation of proinflammatory and profibrotic pathways. The findings indicate ongoing endothelial injury and active vascular remodeling.

Conclusion: Elevated inflammatory and angiogenic markers confirm their role in the pathophysiology of complicated AIO. Their monitoring may improve prognostic assessment and guide individualized treatment

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